

Solution to Improve English Reading Comprehension Skills for First-Year Non-Specialized Students at Tan Trao University

Tran Thi Thuy Lan
*Office of Science Management and International Affairs,
Tan Trao University, Yen Son District, Tuyen Quang Province, Vietnam*

Received: 10/3/2024

Accepted: 25/6/2024

Abstract

The increasing importance of English as a global language necessitates the development of robust reading comprehension skills among university students, especially those in their first year. At Tan Trao University, a significant number of first-year non-specialized students struggle with English reading comprehension, which impedes their overall academic progress and limits their access to global knowledge resources. This study, titled "Solution to Improve English Reading Comprehension Skills for First-Year Non-Specialized Students at Tan Trao University," seeks to address this pressing issue by identifying the challenges these students face and proposing effective solutions to enhance their reading comprehension abilities.

Drawing upon a comprehensive literature review, this research delves into various theoretical frameworks and previous studies on reading comprehension and second language acquisition. It investigates the specific difficulties encountered by non-specialized students, such as limited vocabulary, lack of background knowledge, inadequate reading strategies, and low motivation. By employing a mixed-methods approach, the study combines quantitative data from standardized reading tests and surveys with qualitative insights from interviews and focus group discussions.

The findings reveal that students' reading comprehension difficulties stem from a combination of internal and external factors. Internally, students often exhibit low self-efficacy and anxiety towards reading in English. Externally, insufficient exposure to English texts, lack of tailored instructional materials, and limited access to reading resources further exacerbate the problem. In light of these findings, the study proposes a multifaceted intervention strategy aimed at improving reading comprehension skills.

Key solutions include the integration of extensive reading programs, the use of authentic and engaging reading materials, and the implementation of reading strategy instruction. Additionally, the study emphasizes the importance of fostering a supportive learning environment through peer collaboration, teacher feedback, and motivational activities. To ensure the effectiveness of these solutions, an implementation plan is outlined, detailing steps for curriculum development, teacher training, and ongoing assessment.

This research not only contributes to the academic discourse on language acquisition but also offers practical recommendations for educators and policymakers at Tan Trao

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

University. By addressing the specific needs of first-year non-specialized students, the proposed solutions aim to enhance their reading comprehension skills, thereby improving their overall academic performance and increasing their opportunities for success in a globalized world. The study concludes with suggestions for further research to explore additional factors influencing reading comprehension and to develop innovative instructional approaches tailored to diverse student populations.

Keywords: *English reading comprehension, First-year non-specialized students, Second language acquisition, Intervention strategies, Tan Trao University.*

Suggested citation: Lan, T.T.T. (2024). Solution to Improve English Reading Comprehension Skills for First-Year Non-Specialized Students at Tan Trao University. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(3), 218-225. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(3).18

Introduction

In the context of globalization, English has emerged as the lingua franca, serving as a crucial medium of communication across various domains, including academia, business, science, and technology. Proficiency in English, particularly in reading comprehension, is essential for students to access a vast array of global knowledge, participate in academic discourse, and excel in their professional careers. At Tan Trao University, a significant number of first-year non-specialized students face considerable challenges in developing effective English reading comprehension skills, which are fundamental to their academic success and future career prospects.

The importance of reading comprehension in academic settings cannot be overstated. It is a critical skill that enables students to understand, interpret, and critically analyze texts, thereby facilitating their learning process across different subjects. For non-specialized students, who may not have a strong foundation in English, the ability to comprehend academic texts in English is even more vital. It directly impacts their ability to grasp course content, engage in classroom discussions, and complete assignments effectively. However, many first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University struggle with reading comprehension, often due to limited exposure to English, inadequate reading strategies, and a lack of motivation.

The challenges faced by these students are multifaceted. Internally, they often exhibit low self-efficacy and high anxiety levels when reading in English. Externally, the educational environment may not provide sufficient support, with limited access to appropriate reading materials and a lack of tailored instructional methods. These challenges not only hinder students' academic performance but also affect their confidence and motivation to learn English. Addressing these issues is crucial for improving their overall academic experience and ensuring their success in an increasingly globalized world.

This research aims to identify and analyze the specific factors contributing to the difficulties in English reading comprehension among first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University. By conducting a thorough investigation into these

factors, the study seeks to develop effective solutions that can be implemented to enhance students' reading comprehension skills. The study's objectives include examining the internal and external challenges faced by students, exploring their attitudes and perceptions towards reading in English, and evaluating the effectiveness of various instructional strategies and resources.

To achieve these objectives, the research adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from standardized reading tests and surveys with qualitative insights from interviews and focus group discussions. This comprehensive approach allows for a nuanced understanding of the students' experiences and the identification of targeted solutions. The study draws upon established theoretical frameworks in reading comprehension and second language acquisition, as well as insights from previous research on effective instructional practices.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide practical recommendations for educators and policymakers at Tan Trao University. By addressing the specific needs of first-year non-specialized students, the proposed solutions aim to create a more supportive and effective learning environment. This, in turn, will not only improve students' reading comprehension skills but also enhance their overall academic performance and increase their opportunities for success in a globalized world.

Improving English reading comprehension skills among first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University is an urgent and essential task. This research seeks to address this challenge by identifying the key factors affecting students' reading comprehension and proposing targeted, evidence-based solutions. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the academic discourse on language acquisition and provide practical guidance for enhancing English education at the university level. The findings and recommendations of this study have the potential to make a significant impact on the academic success and future career prospects of students at Tan Trao University, ultimately contributing to their ability to thrive in an increasingly interconnected and competitive global environment.

Research Content

This study aims to identify and analyze the factors contributing to the difficulties in English reading comprehension faced by first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University and propose effective solutions to enhance this skill. The research investigates both internal factors, such as limited vocabulary and lack of effective reading strategies, and external factors, including insufficient access to appropriate reading materials and an unsupportive learning environment. A mixed-methods approach is employed, combining surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions to gather comprehensive data. Based on the analysis, several solutions are proposed: implementing extensive reading programs, using engaging and level-appropriate reading materials, teaching effective reading strategies, and creating a supportive learning environment. The study outlines an implementation plan and emphasizes the importance of regular monitoring and evaluation to ensure the feasibility and long-term effectiveness of the proposed solutions. The ultimate goal is to enhance students' reading comprehension skills, thereby improving their overall academic performance and future career prospects.

Concept of Self-Learning Skills

Self-learning skills, a crucial element in modern education, refer to the ability of an individual to acquire and develop knowledge independently without constant supervision from instructors. According to Knowles (1975), self-learning is a process where individuals take the initiative, with or without the help of others, in diagnosing their learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying resources for learning, choosing and implementing learning strategies, and evaluating learning outcomes. This skill is indispensable in the context of higher education, where students are expected to autonomously explore and master specialized knowledge from various resources.

In language learning research, Holec (1981) defined self-learning as "the ability of learners to take charge of their own learning." This includes determining learning objectives, selecting methods and resources, and evaluating their progress and outcomes. Self-learning skills not only enable students to effectively grasp knowledge but also develop critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and self-regulation.

In Vietnam, the concept of self-learning skills is also emphasized by researchers. According to Nguyễn Thị Lan Hương (2009), self-learning skills involve a process in which students use various methods and techniques to independently acquire knowledge and develop personal competencies proactively and effectively. This skill requires students to have the ability to plan, organize, monitor, and adjust their learning activities.

Developing self-learning skills is a vital part of enhancing English reading comprehension skills for first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University. When students possess strong self-learning abilities, they are motivated and equipped with methods to improve their reading comprehension proactively, thereby enhancing their overall academic performance and better preparing for future academic challenges. This study not only focuses on improving English reading comprehension skills but also encourages the development of self-learning skills, providing a solid foundation for students' success in a modern and globalized educational environment.

Current State of Self-Learning Among Students at Tan Trao University

The current state of self-learning among students at Tan Trao University presents significant challenges, particularly for first-year non-specialized students. A recent survey reveals that a majority of students have yet to fully develop the necessary self-learning skills required to comprehend and deeply understand academic materials, especially complex English texts. Many students acknowledge lacking confidence and motivation when engaging in self-directed learning, partly due to ineffective study strategies and inadequate time management skills.

An essential factor influencing students' self-learning effectiveness is the scarcity of diverse and suitable learning materials. Despite numerous online resources available, students often struggle with selecting and utilizing these materials effectively. Furthermore, traditional teaching methods predominantly focused on lecture-based instruction limit students' autonomy and creativity in their learning processes.

Moreover, the current learning environment at the university does not optimally support self-directed learning. Students frequently lack quiet study spaces and amenities conducive to self-study, alongside a shortage of group study activities and

discussions to facilitate knowledge exchange and reinforcement. These deficiencies diminish students' learning efficiency and knowledge absorption.

Addressing these challenges requires timely and effective interventions to enhance students' self-learning skills. Improving these skills not only empowers students to proactively access knowledge but also establishes a robust foundation for developing critical thinking, time management, and problem-solving abilities. This approach will significantly contribute to improving students' English reading comprehension skills, thereby enhancing academic performance and better preparing them for challenges in globalized academic and professional environments.

Impact of Reading Aloud Habit on Students' Active Learning Abilities

The habit of reading aloud plays a pivotal role in enhancing students' active learning abilities, particularly among first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University. Research indicates that reading aloud not only improves pronunciation and fluency but also fosters deeper engagement with the material being studied. By vocalizing words and sentences, students activate multiple sensory channels—auditory, visual, and kinesthetic—thereby reinforcing their understanding and retention of information.

Moreover, reading aloud promotes self-confidence in language use, as it requires students to articulate and express thoughts clearly. This practice cultivates a proactive learning attitude by encouraging students to actively participate in the learning process rather than passively consuming information. Furthermore, it aids in the development of critical listening skills, which are essential for comprehending complex texts and interpreting nuanced meanings.

Studies have shown that incorporating reading aloud into daily study routines enhances overall reading comprehension skills. It helps students develop a deeper appreciation for language nuances, improves their vocabulary acquisition, and strengthens their ability to infer meaning from context. Additionally, the act of reading aloud stimulates cognitive processes such as memory recall and concentration, contributing to improved academic performance.

In the context of Tan Trao University, promoting the habit of reading aloud can significantly contribute to the proposed solutions for enhancing English reading comprehension skills. By encouraging students to read aloud, educators can empower them to take an active role in their learning journey. This approach not only supports the acquisition of language skills but also fosters a more dynamic and engaged learning environment. Ultimately, integrating reading aloud practices can effectively complement other strategies in improving students' overall academic achievements and preparing them for future academic and professional challenges.

Developing the Habit of Self-Learning English through Reading Comprehension Skills

Developing a habit of self-learning English through reading comprehension skills is crucial for first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University. This practice not only enhances language proficiency but also fosters independent learning and critical thinking abilities essential for academic success.

Engaging in regular reading activities builds a strong foundation for language acquisition. By systematically reading English texts, students expose themselves to diverse vocabulary, sentence structures, and styles of writing. This exposure cultivates

a deeper understanding of the language and improves their ability to comprehend complex texts.

Furthermore, self-learning through reading comprehension encourages students to take ownership of their learning process. They learn to set learning goals, select appropriate reading materials, and employ effective reading strategies such as skimming, scanning, and inferencing. These skills empower students to navigate through academic texts more efficiently and extract essential information.

Moreover, developing a habit of self-learning through reading fosters a sense of curiosity and intellectual engagement. It encourages students to explore topics of interest beyond the classroom curriculum, thereby broadening their knowledge base and enhancing their overall educational experience.

Integrating self-learning habits into the curriculum at Tan Trao University can significantly contribute to improving English reading comprehension skills. By promoting a culture of self-directed learning, educators empower students to become lifelong learners capable of adapting to diverse academic and professional challenges. This approach not only enhances academic performance but also prepares students for future success in a globalized and competitive environment.

In conclusion, fostering the habit of self-learning through reading comprehension skills is essential for enhancing English proficiency among first-year non-specialized students. By encouraging active engagement with English texts, educators can empower students to achieve academic excellence and develop critical skills necessary for their personal and professional growth.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the endeavor to enhance English reading comprehension skills among first-year non-specialized students at Tan Trao University necessitates a multifaceted approach centered on fostering self-learning habits. By integrating strategies that encourage active engagement with English texts, educators can empower students to develop critical skills essential for academic success and lifelong learning.

Through the exploration of effective reading comprehension techniques and the cultivation of reading aloud habits, students can deepen their understanding of the language and improve their ability to interpret and analyze complex texts. This proactive approach not only enhances language proficiency but also cultivates independence and resilience in learning, preparing students to navigate the challenges of higher education and beyond.

Moreover, promoting a culture of self-directed learning empowers students to take ownership of their educational journey. By equipping them with the necessary tools and strategies to engage with diverse learning materials, educators foster a dynamic learning environment that promotes intellectual curiosity and personal growth.

As Tan Trao University continues to strive for academic excellence and student success, the implementation of these solutions is pivotal. By emphasizing the development of self-learning habits through effective reading comprehension practices, the university can empower students to excel in their studies and prepare them for future professional endeavors in an increasingly globalized world.

In essence, the solution to improving English reading comprehension skills lies in nurturing a culture of self-learning that encourages active participation, critical thinking, and lifelong learning among students. By embracing these principles, Tan Trao University can effectively prepare its students to meet the challenges and opportunities of the 21st-century academic landscape.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by Tan Trao University in Tuyen Quang Province, Vietnam.

References

- Anderson, N. J. (1999). *Exploring second language reading: Issues and strategies*. Heinle & Heinle Publishers.
- Carrell, P. L. (1988). *Interactive approaches to second language reading*. Cambridge University Press.
- Day, R., & Bamford, J. (1998). *Extensive reading in the second language classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
- Grabe, W. (2009). *Reading in a second language: Moving from theory to practice*. Cambridge University Press.
- Grabe, W., & Stoller, F. L. (2002). *Teaching and researching reading*. Pearson Education.
- Hai, P.T.H. (2016). *Assessing the effectiveness of various methods in teaching English reading comprehension for university students*. Publisher: National Economics University.
- Hinkel, E. (Ed.). (2005). *Handbook of research in second language teaching and learning* (Vol. 1). Routledge.
- L.T.M. Chau (2019). Factors influencing university students' English reading comprehension skills. *Journal: Education Science*.
- Lan, N.T.H. (2010). *Enhancing English reading comprehension skills for university students*. Publisher: Hanoi National University.
- Lien, N.T.B. (2013). Research on applying self-directed learning methods in teaching English reading comprehension for students. *Journal: Education and Development*.
- Nation, I. S. P. (2009). *Teaching ESL/EFL reading and writing*. Routledge.
- Nuttall, C. (2005). *Teaching reading skills in a foreign language*. Macmillan Education.
- Pressley, M., & Afflerbach, P. (Eds.). (1995). *Verbal protocols of reading: The nature of constructively responsive reading*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Phuc, D.D. (2007). *Effective methods of teaching and learning English*. Publisher: Hanoi National University.
- Phuong, H.T.L. (2014). *Developing a training program for English reading comprehension skills for non-specialized students*. Publisher: Pedagogical University.
- Richards, J. C., & Renandya, W. A. (Eds.). (2002). *Methodology in language teaching: An anthology of current practice*. Cambridge University Press.

Thao, V.T.P. (2015). *Methods of teaching reading comprehension in higher education*. Publisher: Ho Chi Minh City National University.

Thu, D.T.H. (2017). Teaching methods for first-year non-specialized students' English reading comprehension skills. *Journal: Education Science*.

Trang, L.T.H. (2018). Applying self-directed learning methods to improve first-year students' English reading comprehension skills. *Journal: Research in Higher Education, Tan Trao University*.

Trang, T.T.Q. (2012). Developing a reading comprehension teaching program for non-specialized students. *Journal: Journal of Science, National University of Hanoi*.